

Comparative Study of Patients Undergoing Laparoscopic Versus Open Appendectomy

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Introduction

...we have an appendix (a small remnant of a prior ancestor species' intestinal sack) which not only is of no use to us but which can sometimes kill us when it gets clogged up and infected! What kind of god or other "intelligent designer" would design organisms with such useless, imperfect, wasteful, and sometimes even harmful physical features? [1]

Acute appendicitis is one of the most common diseases treated by general surgeons. Appendectomy is the most common acute care operation.

Mortality associated with acute appendicitis and its treatment has dropped from 26 % to as low as 0.2 death per 100000. Mortality associated with perforated appendicitis at an extreme age may approach 5 % or more.

Since its initial description by Semmin in 1983, laparoscopic appendectomy (LA) has struggled to prove its superiority over the open technique. This is in contrast to laparoscopic cholecystectomy, which has promptly become the gold standard for gallstone disease despite little scientific challenge.[2]

Open appendectomy (OA) has withstood the test of time for more than a century since its introduction by McBurney.[3] The procedure is standardized among surgeons and, unlike cholecystectomy, OA is typically completed using a small right lower quadrant incision and postoperative recovery is usually uneventful. It is the second most common general surgical procedure performed in the United States, after laparoscopic cholecystectomy, and the most common intraabdominal surgical emergency, with a lifetime risk of 6%. The overall mortality of OA is around 0.3%; and morbidity, about 11%. [4] Given the large number of procedures done annually, the validation of a minimally invasive technique that would improve outcomes may have a direct impact on patient management and possibly an indirect effect on the economics of health care.

Numerous prospective randomized studies,[5-9] meta-analyses,[10-13] and systematic critical reviews[14-16] have been published on the topic of LA, with a general consensus that the heterogeneity of the measured variables and other weaknesses in the methodology have not allowed to draw definitive conclusions and generalizations.

With this in mind, we have designed a prospective comparative study comparing LA to OA that included independent data collector and statistical analysis.

Aim

To compare the effectiveness and safety of laparoscopic and open appendectomy.

Objective

To compare the effectiveness and safety of laparoscopic and open appendectomy.

The patients admitted with appendicitis were evaluated under following headings:

1. Number of days of stay in hospital.
2. Difference in WBC counts.
3. Pain score after 24 hours and after 48 hours.
4. Intra-operative findings other than appendicitis.
5. Post -operative complications of appendectomy.
6. Post -operative requirement of pain killers (NSAIDs and opioid analgesics).
7. Day of oral feeding tolerance.
8. Day of normal activity after operation.
9. Total cost during stay in hospital.

Materials and Methods

This study was conducted in the department of General Surgery in Holy Family Hospital and Research Centre Mumbai.

It includes a prospective study of cases from October 2010 to September 2012. A total of 100 patients were included in the study. Necessary permission and approval from the hospital administration and ethics committee were taken prior to starting the study. Valid consent was obtained prior to selection of cases.

Study area:

The study was carried out in the General Surgery department of Holy Family Hospital and Research Centre, Mumbai. This is a teaching trust hospital located in the city of Mumbai, catering to the needs of various socioeconomic strata of the local community having a capacity of 232 beds.

Study Design

Patients diagnosed to have appendicitis and have undergone appendectomy.

Study Period

2 years – From 1st October 2010 to 30th September 2012

Study Centre

Holy Family Hospital, Bandra, Mumbai.

Study Sample

100 patients clinically diagnosed appendicitis and confirmed radiologically at Holy Family Hospital.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Patient with lower abdominal pain.
2. Age greater than > 6 year and < 65 years.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Patient with age less than 6 year and more than 65 years.
 2. Patients with associated other intra-abdominal pathology.
 3. Patient with history of previous abdominal surgery.
 4. Patient with associated co-morbid condition affecting patients life style.
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Assessment of Patients

Patients enrolled in the study after taking valid informed consent were evaluated for post operative pain score , post operative recovery, post operative mobilization etc. Patients details were entered in a preformed proforma and data collected was tabulated and analysed statistically.

Management of Patients

Patient admitted in hospital were managed with IV fluids, IV antibiotics, NBM and injectable analgesics. Depending on patient condition, patients were offered Appendectomy and were managed postoperatively with IV medications. Patient were also observed for post operative complications like wound infection, peritonitis etc.

Data Analysis

Thorough history was taken and complete assessment was done pre-operatively. Presence of preoperative pain was assessed.

All patients underwent either open or laparoscopic appendectomy. All patients were followed in hospital from the day of admission to the day of discharge including pre-operative workup, intra-operative monitoring and post operative recovery including pain and analgesics requirement was assessed. All events are documented in preformed proforma. Observations were tabulated on a spread sheet by using Microsoft Excel. Statistical analysis was carried out using SPSS version 15 using Pearson Chi-Square , Likelihood Ratio and Linear-by-Linear Association.

Patients were analysed with respect to:

1. Difference in WBC counts
2. Number of days of stay
3. Pain score after 24 hours and after 48 hours
4. Intra-operative findings other than appendicitis
5. Post operative complications of appendectomy

6. Post operative requirement of pain killers (NSAIDs and opioid analgesics)
7. Day of oral feeding tolerance
8. Day of normal activity after operation
9. Total cost during stay in hospital

Observations & Results

In our study youngest patient was of 9 years age and oldest of 70 years age. Most of them being above 10 years (48 %). And 56 % were females compared to 44 % males in our study.

Age	Number of patients (%)
Less than 10 years	18
10 to 25 years	48
More than 25 years	34

Table 1 : Age group distribution of study population

60 % of acute appendicitis patients underwent laparoscopic appendectomy compared to 40 % who underwent open appendectomy. 25 % of patients with multiple episodes of sub-acute appendicitis underwent laparoscopic appendectomy compared to 75 % patient who underwent open appendectomy. 83 % of chronic appendicitis patient underwent laparoscopic appendectomy.

Type	Laparoscopic appendectomy	Open appendectomy	Number
Acute appendicitis	48 (60 %)	32 (40 %)	80
Multiple episodes of sub-acute appendicitis	2 (25 %)	6 (75 %)	8
Chronic appendicitis	10(83 %)	2(17 %)	12

Table 2: Classification of appendicitis patients and their distribution in study.

Patients coming with lower abdominal pain and clinical diagnosed to have appendicitis were evaluated by hematogram and radiological investigations like USG, barium studies or CT scan abdomen to confirm the diagnosis.

Fig 1 : Classification of appendicitis patients and their distribution in study

Leukocytosis	Open Appendectomy	Laparoscopic Appendectomy
Less than 10000	18.2	81.8
10000-15000	37.0	63.0
More than 15000	87.0	12.5

Table 3 : Leukocytosis in appendicitis

It was observed that patients undergoing open appendectomy, most of them on admission had their leukocyte count more than 15000/cmm (87%). Similarly around 63% of patients undergoing laparoscopic appendectomy had count between the range of 10000 – 15000/cmm. The decision to do an open appendectomy or laparoscopic appendectomy also depended on patients clinical condition, WBC counts, surgeon’s choice or patients request and for economical reasons.

Fig 2: Leukocytosis in appendicitis patients

Appendectomy	Mean stay at hospital (days)
Open appendectomy	6.26
Laparoscopic appendectomy	3.95

Table 4 : Mean stay in hospital of appendectomy patients

Patients undergoing open appendectomy remained in hospital for a longer period of about 6 days compared to laparoscopic appendectomy patient which was of about 4 days. Number of days of stay in hospital is influenced by multiple factors such as severity of appendicitis which in turn decides starting feed after surgery. Invariably some surgeons expecting complicated appendicitis prefer to do an open appendectomy at our institution due to classical teaching. This in turn decides day of oral feed starting and the discharge of patient.

Fig 3: Mean stay in hospital of appendectomy patients

	Open Appendectomy	Laparoscopic Appendectomy
Meckel’s diverticulitis	1(2.56%)	3(4.91%)
Mesenteric lymphadenitis	3(7.69%)	2(3.27%)
Ovarian cyst	1(2.56%)	1(1.63%)

Table 5: Additional findings in appendectomy patients

In our study total 5 (Meckel’s diverticulitis-1, Mesenteric lymphadenitis- 3 and Ovarian cyst- 1) additional findings were seen in laparoscopic appendectomy group compared to 6 (Meckel’s diverticulitis- 3, Mesenteric lymphadenitis- 2 and Ovarian cyst- 1) in open appendectomy group. Even though laparoscopy has an advantage of exploring the complete peritoneal cavity our study does not show significant difference in additional findings in laparoscopic appendectomy group (P = 0.693).

Fig 4: Additional findings in appendectomy patients

Patients were observed for postoperative pain on pain chart which is shown by diagrammatic representation below depicting facial expressions for pain graded from no pain to excruciating pain.

Patient with mild and bearable pain and did not require analgesics fell in category between 1 to 3 scale.

Fig 5: Pain Score Chart

Patient with bearable pain but required analgesics for pain fell in grade between 4 to 6. Patient who could not bear pain and almost always require two different types of analgesics fell in category between 7 to 10.

Appendectomy	Pain score day 0	Pain score day 1
Open appendectomy	5.36	2.74
Laparoscopic appendectomy	2.77	1.30

Table 6 : Post appendectomy pains score

In our study pain was charted at 24 hours post operative period and at 48 hours post operative period. We found average pain in open appendectomy group was 5.36 and 2.74 at 24 hours and 48 hours post operative period respectively. In case of laparoscopic appendectomy group it was 2.77 (P = 0.001) and 1.30 (P = 0.024) at 24 hours and 48 hours post operative respectively. Thus laparoscopic appendectomy has shown to have less pain compared to open appendectomy.

Fig 06: Post appendectomy pain score

	Open appendectomy(%)	Laparoscopic appendectomy(%)
Opioid required	93.3	6.7

Table 7: Opioid requirement in appendectomy patients

Nearly all patients with pain were managed with NSAIDS group of analgesics and 93.3% required opioid analgesic for pain control in first 24 hours in open appendectomy patients and 6.7% in laparoscopic appendectomy patient group.

Fig 07: Opioid requirement in appendectomy patients

Day oral feed	Open appendectomy(%)	laparoscopic appendectomy(%)
0 days	1(3%)	53(87%)
1 day	33(84%)	8(13%)
2 day	5(13%)	-

Table 8: Oral feed tolerance in post appendectomy Patients

Out of 100 patients in the study, 87% of patients from the laparoscopic appendectomy group successfully tolerated oral feeds on the day 0 of surgery while around 84% of the patients from open appendectomy group tolerated oral feed on post-operative day 1. This observation depicts that laparoscopic appendectomy group patients tolerate oral feeds earlier compared to open appendectomy group.

Fig 08: Oral feed tolerance in post appendectomy patients

Appendectomy	Day normal activity
Open appendectomy	5.15
laparoscopic appendectomy	2.42

Table 9: Normal activity achieved in post appendectomy patients

Patients who underwent laparoscopic appendectomy required on an average 2.5 days to resume normal activity compared to open appendectomy group which required on an average 5 days (P = 0.196).

Thus, laparoscopic appendectomy does not show advantage over open appendectomy in terms of early mobilization.

Fig 9: Normal activity achieved in post appendectomy patients

Appendectomy	Total cost (Rs)
Open appendectomy	20171.79
laparoscopic appendectomy	28450.82

Table 10 : Total cost in appendectomy patients

Depending upon the early mobilization, post-operative pain and the cost related to the surgery, the overall cost during the stay in the hospital of the patient changes. It was observed that the patients who underwent open appendectomy had an average stay in hospital for 5 days compared to laparoscopic appendectomy 3 days which may be related to post-operative complications of open appendectomy.

Fig 10: Total cost in appendectomy patients

	Open appendectomy	Laparoscopic appendectomy
Wound infection	4(10.25 %)	1(2.56%)
Intra abdominal infection	2(5.12 %)	-
Urinary retention	3(7.69 %)	-
Pulmonary infection	2(5.12%)	1(2.56 %)

Table 11 : Complications of appendectomy

Of total 13 complications noted in study, majority of them were from open appendectomy group (11 in open appendectomy group and 2 in laparoscopic appendectomy group). More urinary retentions, pulmonary infections, wound infections and intra-abdominal infections are seen in open appendectomy group.

Fig 11 : Complications f appendectomy

Discussion

Laparoscopic appendectomy and open appendectomy have been compared in the past with regards to post-operative pain, post-operative recovery time, total cost etc. This study is aimed to come to a conclusion about benefits and drawbacks, if any, of laparoscopic appendectomy over open appendectomy. The laparoscopic and open appendectomy group were compared on the basis of following parameters:

1. Difference in WBC counts
2. Number of days of stay
3. Pain score after 24 hours and after 48 hours
4. Intra-operative findings additional to appendicitis
5. Post operative complications of appendectomy
6. Post operative requirement of pain killers (NSAIDs and opioid analgesics)
7. Day of oral feeding tolerance
8. Day of normal activity after operation
9. Total cost during stay in hospital

It was observed that laparoscopic appendectomy has an advantage of less post-operative pain, less post-operative analgesic requirement, faster recovery and early feeding. It has also been observed that laparoscopic procedures (appendectomy) is associated with more bowel injuries which is not seen in our study because all procedures done in our hospital were done by skilled senior surgeons and senior residents by an open first port access technique. In our hospital it is routine practice of two consultants doing laparoscopic appendectomy together while open appendectomy is done by single consultant, the cost is more for patient undergoing laparoscopic appendectomy than in open appendectomy. It is also observed that there is not much difference in post-operative oral feed tolerance in both the groups. Open appendectomy has an advantage of three dimensional perception of the anatomy which reduces the complications of bowel injury seen in laparoscopic procedures. Thus, it is difficult to come to a conclusion regarding the superiority of either procedure over the other.

Laparoscopic appendectomy and surgical experience

The outcome of any laparoscopic procedure greatly depends on the experience of the surgeon. In a study of two groups, conducted at Los Angeles, general surgical services operated on 413 patients, and 232 cases underwent the same procedure by trained specialized laparoscopic surgeons.

General surgical services	285 acute	51 gangrenous	67 perforated
Laparoscopic surgeons	126 acute	46 gangrenous	60 perforated

Table 12 : Laparoscopic appendectomy and surgical Experience

10 abscesses occurred post-operatively (2.4%) in the group of patients whose operation was done by general surgical services, and only once case of intra-abdominal abscess (0.025%) were reported in the group of patients whose operation were performed by a standardized laparoscopic method, using skilled dissection, careful use of retrieval bag, proper ligation of stump and thorough peritoneal toilet). This study may be taken to indicate that complications such as intra-abdominal abscess following laparoscopic appendectomy for perforated appendices can be reduced significantly by training.

In our study of total 100 patient diagnosed to have appendicitis clinically and confirmed on radiological investigations, 39 underwent open appendectomy and 61 underwent laparoscopic appendectomy. Complications like Wound infection was seen in 4 patients, Intra abdominal infection was in 2 patients, Urinary retention in 3 patients and Pulmonary infection in 2 patient belonging to open appendectomy group compared to 1 wound infection and 1 pulmonary infection in patient belonging to laparoscopic appendectomy group. Thus complications were less in our study in laparoscopic group. Patient undergoing laparoscopic appendectomy had less pain compared to open appendectomy group. Only 6.7 % of patient required opioid analgesic in first 24 hours of surgery, in laparoscopic appendectomy group. Most of the patients were comfortably discharged by average 6.26 days in open appendectomy group and average 3.96 days in laparoscopic appendectomy group. Laparoscopic appendectomy did show additional findings comparatively but was not statistically significant.

Summary

Total 100 patients admitted to Holy family hospital with lower abdominal pain , with clinical diagnosis of appendicitis and confirmed on USG abdomen pelvis and other radiological investigations were reviewed from day of admission to day of discharge. During the period of 2 years, patients with above finding between age group of 6 years to 65 years were evaluated. Each patient or relative (if patient is minor) were explained in the language best understood by them about the nature of the study. After valid written consent, patients were enrolled in the study.

Patients from the time of admission to discharge were followed up and were observed for :

- Clinical findings,
- Radiological findings,
- Hematological findings,
- Type of operation (open or laparoscopic appendectomy),
- Intra-operative finding other than appendicitis,
- Post operative pain,
- Post operative analgesic required,
- Oral feed tolerance in post-operative period,

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- Mobilization in post operative period,
 - Complications of surgery,
 - Total expenses during the hospital stay
 - Total number of days of stay in hospital.

All details were charted on preformed proforma. The data collected was charted on excel sheet and was statistically analysed.

It was observed that total 100 patients were enrolled in the study. Out of which, 39 belonged to patients who underwent open appendectomy and 61 belonging to group of laparoscopic appendectomy.

Conclusion

1. Majority of patients with WBC count of >15000/cumm underwent open appendectomy and those with WBC count < 10000 underwent laparoscopic appendectomy.
2. Mean stay in the hospital of patients undergoing laparoscopic appendectomy (3.96 days) was less than patients undergoing open appendectomy (6.26 days).
3. Other conditions mimicking acute appendicitis (Meckel's diverticulitis, Mesenteric lymphadenitis and Ovarian cyst) were found out in laparoscopic appendectomy group but were not statistically significant in this study.
4. Pain in patients undergoing laparoscopic appendectomy was comparatively less than patients undergoing open appendectomy.
5. Opioid analgesic requirement in open appendectomy group was more than in laparoscopic appendectomy.
6. Laparoscopic appendectomy group were started on oral feeds earlier than the open appendectomy group.
7. Early mobilization is possible in both open and laparoscopic appendectomy patients.
8. Open appendectomy patient (28.20 %) had more complications compared to laparoscopic appendectomy patients(3.27).
9. Laparoscopic appendectomy incurs additional expenses for the patients of assisting surgeon, compared

to open appendectomy in our study.

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